

Mining, Resource Conflict and Food Security in Nigeria: A Diagnostic Analysis of Coal Mining in Ankpa Communities, Kogi State

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Abstract:

Concerns over the paradox of natural resources leading to frustration, expressed in underdevelopment, poverty, and sometimes conflict, rather than wealth and development, have occupied a central place among scholars, thinkers, and policymakers over the years across the globe. Thus, this study seeks to examine the link between mining, resource conflict and food security in Nigeria. The study adopts the survey research design by collecting primary data through the administration of questionnaires. It adopts simple and descriptive statistics to analyze the primary data while content analysis was employed for the secondary data. The study revealed that mining and conflict are inseparable, for wherever there is resources, there must be agitations and then conflict. Further findings from the research also show a strong connection between mining, conflict, and food security. Hence, it concludes that mining leads to loss of arable farmland, contamination of the water, soil and environmental degradation and that all these are direct threat to food production and security. It therefore, recommends, effective resource governance that will strategically manage and coordinate the mining sector for compliance with environmental standards, diversify the economy and incentivize the agricultural sector.

Keywords: Mining, Resource Conflict, Food Security, Agriculture, Coal Mining.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In addition to the water pollution and soil degradation caused by coal mining in Ankpa, the activities also cause substantial social disruption, dispossession, and displacement, which threaten the local food security in the area. This multidimensional dilemma continues to undermine environmental stability, as well as the integration of social units and the economic activities of the people within these units; therefore, food insecurity in the area continues to grow.

Research has suggested that the coal mining activities in Ankpa and its environs have resulted in the dispossession and displacement of a large number of local people from their original homes and lands. The most affected regions have been documented by the likes of Ikegwonu (2018) and Ambursa et al. (2021), who describe in great detail the massive dispossession of land and the eviction of people from their homes in the mining regions, taking their cultivated lands, and farming fields, but do not compensate and do not provide any support for rehabilitation (Ikegwonu 2018; Ambursa et al. 2021). This displacement affects the relocated farmers and disrupts their farming activities, and therefore severely limits local food production.

Additionally, the deprivation of one's land also means the deprivation of one's productive farming land, the lifeblood of the rural populace of Ankpa. Okorie and Egila (2014) assert that the ineffective implementation of the land and environmental governance framework permits the mining corporations to exercise land grabbing without conscience and thrust the local populace into abysmal poverty and hunger. Dislocated households have often been unable to move to new locations with viable farming land, and thus suffer declining yields of retained food and increased hunger. This phenomenon, dispossession, severs the connection of people to their food and income, compels them to rely on food aid or purchase from neighboring towns and villages, and reduces their capacity to withstand food shocks.

The socio-economic dislocation caused by displacement due to mine expansion hinders access to food as well. Households that once practiced subsistent farming are now with insufficient resources such as land, water, and other resources essential to food cultivation. The loss of these land resources further fuels the impoverishment of the cycle and in turn fosters malnutrition and poor health. The Nigerian Bureau of Statistics has reported that mining-displaced communities in Kogi State suffered loss of household incomes and increased food insecurity, resulting in reliance on food aid and food aid informal markets (NBS, 2023).

Moreover, illegal mining continues with these economic and social disruptions. The news of November 2023 mentions the apprehension of illegal miners in the Ankpa area, which reflects the unregulated and disorderly expansion of the mining industry that totally ignores the social and environmental consequences (Daily Post, 2023). Informal and

illegal miners often trespass on community lands, which displaces local agriculturalists and further degrades land and water resources. The lack of social responsibility in these activities of illegal mining widens the gap of available opportunities and continues the cycle of dispossession. There are significant concerns regarding the effects of dispossession and socio-economic dislocation on the climate and the threat it poses to food security. Dispossessed farmers face struggles with both their income and the productive lands, which in turn jeopardize food availability and the ability to maintain the adaptive capacity to the long-term food systems in the area. Furthermore, the displacement of farmers causes the primary reliance on subsistence farming to be lost, which in turn increases the costs of food and places the more food insecure in the area at greater risk.

This paper, therefore, not only interrogates the nexus between coal mining, resource conflict and food security in Nigeria, but it also lays bare the several associated factors that threaten the country's drive for food sufficiency in particular and obstacles to the fulfillment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals with particular emphasis on Goals 2 (Zero Hunger) and 3 (No Poverty). Thus, the significance of the research outcome cannot be overemphasized in that it will provide more empirical data on the socio-economic realities of the people in the mining areas as well as generate community-specific solutions and recommendations to tackle the coming scourge of food crises and how to bridge the food shortage gap.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Scholars look at mining from two broad perspectives. One perspective is that mining has the potential to spur economic growth and local development through the jobs and revenues mining provides, and the infrastructure it generates (Karl, 1997; Auty, 1993); the second, more critical perspective, is that mining causes environmental and other local harms by disrupting livelihoods, and has weak benefit sharing (Bebbington et al., 2008; Auty, 1993). Most recent syntheses capture that the outcomes are contingent on the context: the ownership, quality of governance, scale, and technology of the particular mining extraction determines whether the net outcomes of mining are beneficial or harmful to the rural community (Wegenast & Beck, 2020). Within the mining literature, those which deal with coal mining are particular about its negative ecological footprint. Coal mining, extraction, and especially the surface and small-scale mining that is characteristic of some parts of Nigeria, is notorious for removing vegetation and topsoil, and for the construction of spoil heaps and drainage channels which lead to accelerated erosion and changes in the hydrology (Zubairu et al., 2022; Ahmad et al., 2025). These biophysical changes and numerous other impacts include the risk of acid mine drainage and the bio-accumulation of heavy metals with negative for soils and waters used for agriculture, irrigation, and drinking (Umoru et al., 2024; Ahmad et al., 2025).

The Food and Agriculture Organization has defined food security since 2008 as a multi-layered phenomenon and a combination of availability, access, utilization, and stability. In recent community livelihood studies, food security has been shown to be influenced by variables such as crop yield, household income diversification, labor availability, market integration, and natural capital (Thornton et al. 2019). This definition is substantial considering that mining can determine food security by physical (soil, water, air) and socio-economic (employment, income, land access) means.

In contrast to earlier versions of mining and food security, recent research has shown a more direct relationship. For example, recent cross-country econometric studies show that, in some cases, mining can lead to reduced food production, loss of food access, and overall poor food security, particularly in countries with weak governance and poor environmental control (Wegenast and Beck 2020). In small-scale mining (ASM) case studies, there is a more nuanced 'double-edged' relationship, whereby ASM provides incomes that allow for food access in the short term, but in the long term, the agricultural land is lost, soil degradation occurs, and the availability of the agricultural labor force is reduced (Hilson 2016; Poignant 2022).

Regional and local studies with emphasis on Ankpa and Kogi State align empirically on coal mining related environmental pathways and food insecurity. Kogi East comparative soil studies indicate lower crop productivity on mined sites than on control sites due to reduction of soil organic matter, changing of soil pH, and nutrient mining (Ahmad et al. 2025). Okobo and Odagbo water quality studies indicate mining related effluents by documenting water turbidity, high total dissolved solids, and metals which limits water for both irrigation and livestock (Umoru et al. 2024). Air quality studies in mining towns Ankpa indicate high particulate matter and dust deposition which restricts health of crops and labor (Ahmad & Ameh 2024). These local studies composite the proximate pathways (soil degradation, water contamination, and air pollution) along which coal mining erodes the food insecurity proxy availability and accessibility in the households of Ankpa.

Certainly, interdisciplinary socio-economic and governance studies of Ankpa highlight paradoxes in the literature: while documentation of the mining sector demonstrates profit accumulation in the shorter-term, it does not consider longer term erosion of productive assets, land, and livelihood diversification and withdrawal of participation in subsistence agriculture and the consequent food instability (Ahmad, et al, 2025; Daily Post, 2023). Noteworthy, several authors suggest the synthesis of environmental chemistry with agronomic and food governance metrics to better understand and document the disparate outcomes which undermine policy development in the area and result in loss of the potential for adaptive policy and governance in Ankpa (Wegenast and Beck, 2020).

3. METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a mixed-method research design to investigate the consequences of coal mining on food security in Ankpa, Kogi state, Nigeria, with the aim of attaining a holistic understanding of the studied phenomena (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The mixed-method design enabled the researcher to carry out triangulation with the quantitative findings on the perceived impact of coal mining on food security especially following the consequential effects on the soil, water, and livelihoods to be supplemented with qualitative findings on food security and experiences of the community. The data was collected from the residents of Ankpa mining communities affected by coal mining activities using survey questionnaires.

The question in the survey adopted a 5 scale Likert questionnaire in measuring the effects of coal mining on agricultural activities, access to water and land, income and food security of households. The secondary data were obtained from document review, government publications, and previous research on coal mining, environmental degradation, and food security. Although, coal mining in Ankpa local government area takes place in several communities such as Odobi, Ika Odelto, Engema, Okobo, Ojeke, Agumagu, Ika Ilori, Odoagbo, Odokpono, Utakpa, Awo Akpali, among others. Participants for this study are drawn households within mining communities of Okobo, Odoagbo and Odokpono. The justification for this is because all mining communities shared similar experiences and features in terms of effects and consequences. The total population of Ankpa Local Government Area (LGAs). According to the 2006 population census is put at 267,353. Using Yamane Sample Size Formula for finite populations, $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$, where n is the sample size, N is the population, and e is the margin of error set at 5%, (Yamane, 1967). Since the estimated total population of Ankpa Local Government Area is 267,353, the sample size is estimated to be around 399. Therefore, 400 questionnaires were distributed proportionally across the three study areas.

In order to obtain proportional representation from each ward and coal-mining impacted settlements, stratified random sampling technique was utilized for better accuracy and reliability of results (Babbie, 2020) as well as to generalize results to a wider population. The data collected from surveys were processed using a variety of descriptive and inferential statistics, such as frequency distributions, and percentages for the quantitative field, while the thematic content analysis was applied to secondary data on the disruption of livelihoods, agricultural productivity, and household food security (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study employs the Resource Curse Theory, which was first formalized by Richard Auty in 1993 in *Sustaining Development in Mineral Economies*, as the 'paradox of abundance.' Auty argued that countries with an abundance of minerals and oil resources, as compared to those without, are economically worse off and experience deterioration in their economic development. This anomaly was further documented in the works of Sachs and Warner (1995, 2001) as being negatively correlated with economic growth. Other prominent theorists include Karl in *The Paradox of Plenty* (1997) who advanced the notion of the oil wealth paradox and its political implications; Ross (2001, 2012) who theorized about the nexus of oil, authoritarianism, and civil strife, as well as the paradox of increased female discrimination. The theory rests on the premise that certain countries, by virtue of being resource wealthy, tend to undercapitalize other sectors of the economy including farming and manufacturing resulting in the resource Curse and mono-product economic systems (Auty 1993).

The assumption is that resource wealth lessens the motivation for economic diversification. Foreign resource-rich countries experience currency appreciation which in turn reduces the competitiveness of other exporting sectors (Corden & Neary, 1982). This theory presumes that the abundance of resources attracts elite political control, corrupt patronage, and political capture. Governments prioritize the capture of these resource rents rather than national investments and development (Karl 1997 and Ross 2001). The theory presumes that if there are no sufficient and accountable institutions, then resource wealthy countries will not transform their resource wealth into development, resulting in poor governance, a lack of regulatory control and poor service delivery (Mehlum, Moene & Torvik, 2006).

Resource Curse Theory aptly explains the intersections of food security and coal mining in Nigeria. Abundant natural resource acquisitions by a country lead to adverse negative developmental and economic growth if the country remains extraction-dependent, extraction-captive, has poor governance, and fails to diversify economically. Evidence of the theory is seen in the increasing neglect of agriculture as the dominant food producer sector with rising coal extraction and concentration by the state. More coal mining means a less investment in other agricultural activities, a slower agricultural labor supply, and decreasing active farming. The theory can also be applied to the poor outcomes of coal mining, on land and indirectly on food production, through the loss of land, deforestation, water pollution, and the degradation of farming productive systems.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section of the study presents the result of the data collected from the field through the administration of questionnaires to respondents across the study area. 400 structured questionnaires were distributed and only one was missing representing 100% retrieval rate base on the 399-sample size earlier stated. The result is therefore presented using simple descriptive statistics via tables and frequency distributions.

Table 5.1: Occupational distribution of respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Farming	289	72.4%
Trading	78	19.6%
Artisan	21	5.3%
Others	11	2.7%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

The table 5.1 above represent the occupational distribution of respondents. Data collected confirmed the dominant occupation of the people in the area to be farming with a whopping 72% of respondents asserting to be farmers. About 19.6% of the respondents are traders, they mostly trade in agricultural outputs and farm produce. A mere 5.5% of the people are artisans and only about 2.7% of the respondents either do other jobs or have no job. These findings suggest a major dependent on agriculture for survival, food supply and livelihood, a pointer to the fact that whatever affect that will ultimately affect their livelihood.

Objective one: Perceived effects of coal mining on food security in Ankpa mining Communities in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 5.2: Has coal mining negatively affected livelihood and food availability in your area?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	356	89.2%
No	41	10.3%
Don't Know	2	0.5%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

An overwhelming majority (89.2%) of the respondents assert that mining negatively affected their livelihood and food availability. While about 10.3% of the total respondents claimed otherwise and only a paltry few (0.5%) were unaware. This is also suggestive that not only is there a relationship between coal mining and food security, there is significantly negative on food security.

Table 5.3: Have you experienced any form of resource conflict in your area?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	377	94.4%
No	22	5.6%
Don't Know	-	-
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

An overwhelming majority of respondents confirmed the existence of resource conflict across the study area with a total of 94.4% responding YES to the question. Only an insignificant minority claimed otherwise perhaps due to lack of clear understanding of the question or some sort of sentiment. This revelation aligns with the argument among resource scholars who claimed that conflict is most likely wherever there is resources to mine or exploit.

Table 5.4: Have you experienced any loss of income, livelihood, or food availability in your area due to resource conflict and coal mining activities?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	337	84.5%
No	62	15.5%
Don't Know	-	-
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

Conflict and mining have been identified as a major threat to income, livelihood, and food security in the mining communities of Ankpa. This is shown above in table 5.4 where majority of the respondents (about 84%) agreed to the assertion while only a few (about 15%) were against it. This again has further reiterated the link between mining, conflict and food security.

Table 5.5: How has coal mining negatively affected livelihood and food availability in your area?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
a. Destruction of farmlands	110	27.6%
b. Water and environmental pollution	123	30.8%
c. Increase food prices	59	14.8%
d. Young people no longer engage in farming	107	26.8%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

The table 5.5 above shows water and environmental pollution as the most significant area of effect from mining activities in the study areas. About 30.8% claimed that mining have affected their livelihood and food availability through the pollution of the water sources and environmental degradation. Followed closely is the loss of farmlands with about 27.6% while about 26.8% of the respondents claimed coal mining discouraged young people from farming thereby affecting their livelihood and food availability. On the other hand, only about 14.8% point to increase in food prices as the effect of coal mining in their area on food security.

Table 5.6: What factors that threatens food production and food availability in Ankpa mining communities?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
a. Loss of farmlands	105	26.3%
b. Water and environmental pollution	143	35.8%
c. Rural-Urban Migration	75	18.8%
e. Resource Conflict	76	19.1%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

Objective Two: Perceived effect resource conflict on food security in Ankpa mining communities.

Table 5.7: Have you experienced any form of resource conflict in your area?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	368	92.2%
No	26	6.5%
Don't Know	5	1.3%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5.7 above shows not only high level of awareness of resource conflict but affirmed the existence of it as majority of the respondents (92.2%) assert that they have experienced resource conflict within their domain. While a combine 7.8% of the respondents are either not aware or claimed no conflict happened.

Table 5.8: How has resource conflict affected food security in Ankpa mining communities?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
a. Tension reduced productivity in the community	99	24.9%
b. Prevent free access and movement to and from farms	121	30.4%
c. Contentious lands cannot be utilized for agricultural practices	75	18.5%
e. Reduced manpower for the agro sector	104	26.1%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

The table above shows the identified factors threatening food security in the sampled communities to include: how conflict cause tension that in turn reduced productivity, prevent free access and movement to and from farms, contentious lands cannot be used for farming purposes thereby reducing availability of farming space, and lastly, reduced manpower as a result of the shift towards mining sector also threatens food production in these communities who one depended on agriculture for survival and means of livelihood.

Table 5.9: What are the factors that threatens food security and availability in your community?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
a. Water and environmental pollution		35.8%
b. Loss of farmland		26.3%
c. Rural-urban migration		18.8%
d. Resource conflicts		19%
Total	399	100

Sources: Field Survey, 2025

As regards the factors that threatens food production and availability in Ankpa mining communities, majority of the respondents (35.8%) pointed water and environmental pollution as the major threat to food security in the area. 26.3% are of the opinion that loss of farmland is also a factor threatening food security. About 18.8% and 19% of the respondents believed rural-urban migration and resource conflicts are equally significant factors threatening food production and availability in the area.

5.1 Discussion

The Ankpa mining communities were formerly agrarian people depending mostly on agriculture as means of livelihood and food supply source. This is confirmed as an overwhelming majority of the respondents (72%) claimed to be farmers. Even the few who are either traders or artisans are dependent on agricultural outputs and patronage. This findings from the research shows that anything that affect agriculture in the area will definitely affect their lives and community in a very significant way. This was aptly captured in the submissions of Ikegwuonu, (2018) and Hilson, (2016). When they argued that coal mining has significantly uttered the livelihood of the people in Ankpa mining area by dispossessing them of their arable farmland and increasing the rate of poverty and hunger.

Also, on the effects of coal mining on food availability in the area, the findings show that coal mining has negatively affected food production and mining with about 89% of the respondents affirming the negative effect of mining on their livelihood and food security. These findings align with the argument of Nwajiuba, (2005) who argued that coal mining is a direct threat to food security and general livelihood of the rural people in mining areas. In addition to that and in more specific terms, the study revealed ways and areas by which coal mining has specifically affected food availability and production in the area. It shows among other things that, destruction of farmland, water and environmental pollution, increased food prices and the loss of interest among young people in farming activities are major areas mining of coal has affected food production and availability.

This position is in tandem with the studies of Okpara, Eze, & Agwu, (2018) which argued that environmental degradation is one of the major threat to the survival of the mining communities, and Poignant, (2022) emphasized loss of farmland and environmental destruction as the major effect of coal mining and Wegenast, & Beck, (2020) on the other hand assert that the combination of factors such as loss of farmland, water pollution and environmental degradation increases the poverty of the mining communities. Finally, the study revealed other specific factors threatening food security in the area, which include loss of farmland through explorations (via pit digging), rural-urban migration (migration for people to other villages or urban centers as a result of alterations in the known livelihood by mining activities), water and environmental pollution, and resource conflict. The combination of these factors has been identified as a major threat to food production, food security, and the survival of the people in the mining communities of Ankpa local government area of Kogi state.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has exhaustively examined the impact of coal mining and resource conflict on food security in Nigeria using selected Ankpa mining communities as a point of reference. It was therefore established that there is a very strong nexus between coal mining and food security, especially in the study area. Findings from the field survey and the extant literature reiterate the connection. It shows clearly how mining leads to dispossession, loss of farmlands, reduced focus on agriculture and destroy environment resulting to water and air pollution, deforestation, soil contamination among other factors that are capable of affecting agricultural practices, output and food production in an area depending of agriculture as source of food. Hence, the study concludes that coal mining in Ankpa has resulted to shortage of food production and availability, increase cost and access to food, increased poverty and undermine the communities' sustainability.

Furthermore, the study argued that mining and resource conflict are inseparable, and conflict over resource can lead to long-term negative effect on agriculture and p=food production. Violent conflict over ownership of land can obstruct agricultural practices and discourage farming. It further argued that with the current rate of environmental degradation and water contamination occasioned by mining of coal in the area, basic agro-products which were hitherto produced locally will be imported. The implication of this are poverty, conflict and underdevelopment. It therefore, recommend, effective resource governance that will strategically manage and coordinate the mining sector for compliance with environmental standards, diversify the economy and incentivize the agricultural sector.

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